

http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

WebPage

All (1)

WebPage	
ID: http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/#webpage	
@type	WebPage
@id	http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/#webpage
url	http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/
inLanguage	pt_PT
name	Marketing Digital Tools – Agência de Marketing Digital Ecommerce
datePublished	2019-02-02T15:11:19+00:00
dateModified	2020-02-04T12:22:30+00:00
isPartOf	
@type	WebSite
@id	http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/#website
url	http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/
name	Marketing Digital Tools
potentialAction	
@type	SearchAction
@id	http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/#searchaction
target	
@type	EntryPoint
urlTemplate	http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/?s={search_term_string}
query-input	
@type	PropertyValueSpecification
valueRequired	http://schema.org/True
valueName	search_term_string
publisher	
@type	Organization
@id	http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/#organization
url	http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/
name	Marketing Digital Tools
logo	
@type	ImageObject
@id	http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/#logo
caption	Logo Marketing Digital Tools
url	http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-MDT-ICON-92-dpi-150x90-1.png
width	125
height	82
image	
@type	ImageObject
@id	http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/#logo
caption	Logo Marketing Digital Tools
url	http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-MDT-ICON-92-dpi-150x90-1.png
width	125
height	82

```

1 <!doctype html>
2 <html lang="pt-PT">
3
4 <head>
5 <meta charset="UTF-8">
6 <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, ini
7 <link rel="profile" href="https://gmpg.org/xfn/11">
8
9 <title>Marketing Digital Tools &#8211; Agência de Marke
10 <link rel='dns-prefetch' href='//s.w.org' />
11 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Marketi
12 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Marketi
13 <script type="text/javascript">
14 window._wpemojiSettings = {"baseUrl": "https://s.w
15 !function(e,a,t){var r,n,o,i,p=a.createElement("can
16 </script>
17 <style type="text/css">
18 img.wp-smiley,
19 img.emoji {
20 display: inline !important;
21 border: none !important;
22 box-shadow: none !important;
23 height: 1em !important;
24 width: 1em !important;
25 margin: 0 .07em !important;
26 vertical-align: -0.1em !important;
27 background: none !important;
28 padding: 0 !important;
29 }
30 </style>
31 <link rel='stylesheet' id='wp-block-library-css' href='htt
32 <link rel='stylesheet' id='wc-block-style-css' href='http://pl
33 <link rel='stylesheet' id='dashicons-css' href='http://plugin1
34 <link rel='stylesheet' id='everest-forms-general-css' href='ht
35 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-layout-css' href='http:
36 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-small-screen-css' href='
37 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-general-css' href='http
38 <style id='woocommerce-inline-inline-css' type='text/css'>
39 .woocommerce form .form-row .required { visibility: visible; }
40 </style>
41 <link rel='stylesheet' id='font-awesome-css' href='http://plug
42 <link rel='stylesheet' id='zakra-style-css' href='http://plugi
43 <style id='zakra-style-inline-css' type='text/css'>
44 @media (min-width: 1200px) { .tg-container{max-width: 1200px;}#
45 .tg-primary-menu > div ul li a{font-family: -apple-system, blin
46 </style>
47 <link rel='stylesheet' id='zakra-woocommerce-style-css' href='
48 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-css' href='http://p
49 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-animations-css' href='htt
50 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-frontend-css' href='http:
51 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-global-css' href='http://
52 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-post-24-css' href='http:/
53 <link rel='stylesheet' id='google-fonts-1-css' href='https://f
54 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-shared-0-css' href=
55 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-fa-solid-css' href=
56 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-fa-brands-css' href=
57 <script type='text/javascript' src='http://plugin11.marketingdi
58 <script type='text/javascript' src='http://plugin11.marketingdi
59 <link rel='https://api.w.org/' href='http://plugin11.marketingdi
60 <link rel="canonical" href="http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltoo
61 <link rel="alternate" type="application/json+oembed" href="http
62 <link rel="alternate" type="text/xml+oembed" href="http://plugi
63 <noscript><style>.woocommerce-product-gallery{ opacity: 1 !
64 <meta property="og:title" content="Marketing Digital Tools
65 <meta property="og:type" content="article">
66 <meta property="og:url" content="http://plugin11.marketingdigit
67 <meta property="og:locale" content="pt_PT">
68 <meta property="og:site_name" content="Marketing Digital Tools">
69 <meta property="article:published_time" content="2019-02-02T15:
70 <meta property="article:modified_time" content="2020-02-04T12:2
71 <meta property="og:updated_time" content="2020-02-04T12:22:30+0
72 <meta name="twitter:card" content="summary_large_image">
73 <style type="text/css">
74 .site-title,
75 .site-description {
76 position: absolute;
77 clip: rect(1px, 1px, 1px, 1px);
78 }
79 </style>
80 <link rel="icon" href="http://plugin11.marketingdigital
81 <link rel="icon" href="http://plugin11.marketingdigitaltools.co
82 <link rel="apple-touch-icon-precomposed" href="http://plugin11.

```